

Πνεῦμα κατανύξεως.

The U.S.A have troubles, but these troubles are not Edward Snowden and Julian Assange. One big trouble is ignorance combined with incompetence and incapacity of the governmental departments and agencies to recognize real troubles and threats for the American people. The failure to act in a right and proper way is only a consequence of these. More dangerous as the CoVid pandemic is a pandemic of stupidity and magnification of the staff involved in maintenance of dysfunctional state and its dysfunctional laws, dysfunctional political system, dysfunctional governmental bodies, oversized state departments and agencies. {1–2}

Edward Snowden revealed in his book published 2013 one real trouble named a dysfunctionality of the constitution {3}. The American constitution resembles a tin whose use-by date is expired for a long time and whose content is putrid.

The federal law enforcement departments and agencies and their employees are simply unable to apply appropriate U.S. federal laws intended to combat monopolization, organized crime and other kinds of breach of the law {4–8}. Although they have a right to maintain the law and public order, they simply refuse to exercise it.

Numerous organizations operating free in the U.S.A. are simply branches of German, European and transnational mafia, among them the International Publishers Association based in Switzerland {9–10}; the World Association of News Publishers based in Switzerland, Germany and France {11–12}; Springer Nature originated from Germany {13–14}; the International Psychoanalytical Association, company and „charity“ IPA LBG registered in England and Wales under registered numbers 3496765 and 1071752 respectively {15}; the World Medical Association based in France {16}; the World Psychiatric Association based in Switzerland; the World Wide Web still associated with the staff of CERN based in Switzerland {17}; the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization based in France accompanied by the International Science Council based as well in France and the World Intellectual Property Organization based in Switzerland; the United Nations World Food Programme accompanied by Nestlé, Novartis, and the World Trade Organization based in Switzerland; the North Atlantic Treaty Organization whose current secretary general is simply a lobbyist of the Norway's sovereign wealth fund; the Bank for International Settlements based in Switzerland; Vatican and Catholic Church {18–20}; as well as other organizations not mentioned here but listed in the Yearbook of International Organizations {21} or somewhere else.

Both U.S. public health and education systems are in a disastrous condition more precisely defined as seriously ill. For example, the annual number of ESRD cases in the U.S.A. grown from 56,402 in 1980 to 746,557 in 2017 {22}. Other example: Medical error is the third leading cause of death in

the U.S. {23}. Another example: „Much of the scientific literature, perhaps half, may simply be untrue.“ {24}

Neither American voters nor their representatives but domestic and transnational corporations decide, or to be more precise, dictate by means of the technocratic brainwashing what Americans consume (see, eat, drink, buy), do, and whom they elect. {25–29}

Considering the circumstances of the abrogation of the rule of law {30} I accuse the staff of the United States Department of Homeland Security, the United States Intelligence Community, the United States National Security Council, the United States Homeland Security Council, the Federal Bureau of Investigation, the United States Departments of Justice, Defense, Agriculture, Education, Labor, Treasury, Health, National Institutes of Health, the United States Food and Drug Administration, the Council of the Inspectors General on Integrity and Efficiency, the National Science Foundation of neglect of obvious facts, of irresponsibility by neglect of their duty to act in response to these obvious facts, of creating an unlawful consolidation of institutional powers and misuse of superior social position for self-posturing and self-service, of systematic waste of resources as a result of the superiority complex (Überheblichkeitswahn).

But for those who are self-seeking and who reject the truth and follow wickedness, there will be wrath and anger. {31–33}

References.

1. Christopher Hood. Administrative Diseases: Some Types of Dysfunctionality in Administration. Public Administration, 1974, 52: 439-454.
2. Dana Priest and William Arkin. Top Secret America: The Rise of the New American Security State. Little, Brown and Company, 2011.
3. Edward James Snowden. Everything You Know About the Constitution is Wrong. Folcourt Press, 2013.
4. National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2017, Subtitle F, Human Rights Sanctions, SEC. 1261: Global Magnitsky Human Rights Accountability Act.
<https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/senate-bill/2943/text>
5. Countering America's Adversaries Through Sanctions Act of 2017 (CAATSA).
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/legislation/hr-3364-countering-americas-adversaries-through-sanctions-act>

6. Above mentioned laws are cited also in: A. Poleev. Letters to the American people. Enzymes, 2018. <http://enzymes.at/download/letters.pdf>
7. H.Res.856 - Opposing kleptocracy around the world and supporting efforts to develop an effective, independent International Anti-Corruption Court. 116th Congress (2019-2020)
<https://www.congress.gov/bill/116th-congress/house-resolution/856/text>
8. Executive Order on Preventing Online Censorship
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/executive-order-preventing-online-censorship/>
9. International Publishers Association: List of Members.
<https://internationalpublishers.org/about-ipa-menu/ipa-membership>
10. International Publishers Association: Publishers & Librarians.
<https://internationalpublishers.org/our-work/publishers-librarians>
11. World Association of News Publishers: List of members.
<https://www.wan-ifra.org/list-of-members>
12. World Association of News Publishers: National Associations.
<https://www.wan-ifra.org/national-associations>
13. Springer. In: A. Poleev. Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis. Enzymes, 2020.
<http://enzymes.at/download/ppe.pdf>
14. All editors of Nature Human Behaviour (and most other journals) simply represent universities, i.e. academic mafia:
<https://www.nature.com/nathumbehav/about/editors>
15. Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.
<http://www.enzymes.at/letters/IPA.pdf>
16. Members of the World Medical Association.
<https://www.wma.net/who-we-are/members/>
17. 30th Anniversary of the World Wide Web.
<https://web30.web.cern.ch/>
18. Desacralization of Vatican.
<http://enzymes.at/judgments/Vatican.pdf>

19. Auflösung katholischer Kirche.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/Zerschlagung.pdf>

20. Declaratio Regis.

<http://assembly.re/commandments/reunion.pdf>

21. The Yearbook of International Organizations published by the Union of International Associations.

<https://uia.org/yearbook>

22. US Renal Data System 2019 Annual Data Report: Epidemiology of Kidney Disease in the United States.

<https://www.usrds.org/media/2371/2019-executive-summary.pdf>

23. Martin A Makary, Michael Daniel. Medical error—the third leading cause of death in the U.S. BMJ 2016; 353 :i2139.

<http://www.bmj.com/content/353/bmj.i2139>

24. Richard Horton. Offline: What is medicine's 5 sigma? The Lancet, 2015, 385, 9976: 1380.

[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(15\)60696-1/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(15)60696-1/fulltext)

25. Robin Truth Goodman, Kenneth J. Saltman. Strange Love: How We Learn to Stop Worrying and Love the Market. Rowman & Littlefield, 2002.

26. Jonathan Tepper, Denise Hearn. The Myth of Capitalism: Monopolies and the Death of Competition. Wiley, 2018.

27. Jake Klyczek. School World Order: The Technocratic Globalization of Corporatized Education. Trine Day, 2019.

28. Fakepedia: Wikipedia editors paid to protect Political, Tech, and Media.

<https://www.breitbart.com/tech/2019/03/26/wikipedia-editors-paid-to-protect-political-tech-and-media-figures/>

29. Camille D.Ryan, Andrew J.Schaul, Ryan Butner, John T.Swarthout. Monetizing disinformation in the attention economy: The case of genetically modified organisms (GMOs). European Management Journal. Volume 38, Issue 1, February 2020, Pages 7-18.

30. Demand for recognition.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/demand.pdf>

31. τοῖς δὲ ἐξ ἐριθείας καὶ ἀπειθοῦσι τῇ ἀληθείᾳ πειθομένοις δὲ τῇ ἀδικίᾳ, ὄργῃ καὶ θυμῷ. Πρὸς Ῥωμαίους 2:8

32. Abomination of desolation.

<http://enzymes.at/judgments/abomination.pdf>

33. Decision on imposition of sanctions against criminal organizations and their members.

<http://constitution.fund/judgments/truth.pdf>